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Dentate gyrus is needed for memory retrieval

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35 **ABSTRACT**

36

37 The hippocampus is crucial for acquiring and retrieving episodic and contextual
38 memories. In previous studies, the inactivation of dentate gyrus (DG) neurons by
39 chemogenetic- and optogenetic-mediated hyperpolarization led to opposing conclusions
40 about DG's role in memory retrieval. One study used Designer Receptors Exclusively
41 Activated by Designer Drugs (DREADD)-mediated clozapine N-oxide (CNO)-induced
42 hyperpolarization and reported that the previously formed memory was erased, thus
43 concluding that dentate gyrus is needed for memory maintenance, The other study used
44 optogenetic with halorhodopsin induced hyperpolarization and reported and dentate
45 gyrus is needed for memory retrieval. We hypothesized that this apparent discrepancy
46 could be due to the length of hyperpolarization in previous studies; minutes by
47 optogenetics and several hours by DREADD/CNO. Since hyperpolarization interferes
48 with anterograde and retrograde neuronal signaling, it is possible that the memory
49 engram in the dentate gyrus and the entorhinal to hippocampus trisynaptic circuit was
50 erased by long-term, but not with short-term hyperpolarization. We developed and applied
51 an advanced chemogenetic technology to selectively silence synaptic output by blocking
52 neurotransmitter release without hyperpolarizing DG neurons to explore this apparent
53 discrepancy. We performed *in vivo* electrophysiology during trace eyeblink in a rabbit
54 model of associative learning. Our work shows that the DG output is required for memory
55 retrieval. Based on previous and recent findings, we propose that the actively functional
56 anterograde and retrograde neuronal signaling is necessary to preserve synaptic memory
57 engrams along the entorhinal cortex to the hippocampal trisynaptic circuit.

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66 INTRODUCTION

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68 The hippocampus plays a crucial for encoding, storing, and retrieving memories, such as
69 those found in classical trace eyeblink conditioning, a prototypical model to study
70 declarative memory¹, the association of spatial and sensory cues², and conflict
71 resolution³. It comprises adjacent cortical regions: the dentate gyrus (DG), CA3, CA2, and
72 CA1⁴⁻⁶. In the DG, new memories are distinguished from the older ones, such as for
73 spatial and contextual representation^{7,8} for pattern separation⁹ and encoding, retrieval,
74 and discrimination of episodic memories¹⁰. In the CA3, recurrent synaptic connections
75 are formed, which appear necessary for pattern completion and memory recall¹¹.
76 Environmental cues induce activation of cell assemblies that constantly adapt to changes
77 in external signals and participate in pattern completion, facilitated by EC-CA3 and EC-
78 CA1 synaptic interactions to print memory traces across the EC-trisynaptic circuits^{12,13}.
79 Concurrent EC input to the dendrites of the DG granule cells^{14,15} in concert with pre- and
80 post-synaptic NMDA receptors is required for plasticity^{16,17}. This emerging evidence
81 suggests that memory engrams could be distributed throughout the brain^{1,18,19}.

82 To investigate whether DG plays a role in memory retrieval, a previous study used
83 Designer Receptors Exclusively Activated by Designer Drugs (DREADD)-mediated
84 clozapine N-oxide (CNO)-induced hyperpolarization²⁰ to inhibit the spiking activity of DG
85 cells. Remarkably, the study reported that the memory was erased (after hyperpolarizing
86 DG cells for several hours), suggesting that DG is not needed for memory retrieval²¹. It
87 was thus concluded that DG is required for memory maintenance. Notably, another study
88 suggested the opposite with optogenetic-mediated hyperpolarization of DG cells for only
89 a few minutes, namely that the DG is required for memory retrieval²².

90 It is conceivable that DREADD-mediated hyperpolarization of DG blocked both
91 anterograde and retrograde neuronal signaling over a long-term period (several hours),
92 which was sufficient to erase the memory engrams along the EC-trisynaptic circuits,
93 without leaving an intact copy to re-establish a memory engram once DREADD was
94 switched-off. On the other hand, light-induced hyperpolarization of the DG by
95 optogenetics did not erase the memory engrams enabling memory retrieval when the light
96 was switched-off. The differences in these two procedures could be due to the duration

97 of hyperpolarization: DREADD/CNO-induced hyperpolarization can last several
98 hours^{21,23}. In contrast, optogenetic-induced hyperpolarization in the study was faster and
99 lasted only a few minutes²².

100 Considering the results obtained with these two procedures, we hypothesized that
101 silencing DG output DG synaptic output without hyperpolarizing them would not erase the
102 memory engram even if performed over several days, and memory retrieval would be
103 enabled after un-silencing of synaptic transmission. To test this idea, we developed the
104 next-generation technology based on tetanus toxin light chain (TeTxLC) for virus-
105 delivered Inducible Silencing of Synaptic Transmission (vINSIST)²⁴. TeTxLC specifically
106 cleaves synaptobrevin-2, a key vesicular protein involved in evoked synaptic transmission
107 for selective silencing of the presynaptic output only. With the vINSIST-2 system, we
108 targeted the DG in alert-behaving rabbits. We used the trace eyeblink conditioning
109 paradigm to investigate whether the memory engram would be either erased as in the
110 previous study with DREADD/CNO-mediated DG inhibition²¹ or can be reactivated
111 (retrieved) as in the other study with optogenetic-mediated DG inhibition²². Our results
112 show that silencing DG output with vINSIST²⁴ does not erase the memory engram, which
113 is reactivated for memory retrieval after un-silencing synaptic transmission.

114 Both previous methods^{21,22} based on neuronal hyperpolarization affect the
115 electrical state of all the DG neurons. This implies that the activity manipulation was
116 generalized, unspecific, and unlocalized, involving many mechanisms beyond synaptic
117 release. The vINSIST method²⁴ is designed to functionally disconnect circuits by
118 selectively interrupting the neurotransmitter release mechanism, which is a specifically
119 localized and more subtle targeted manipulation directed specifically towards interfering
120 with the synaptic output of these cells.

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122

123 **RESULTS**

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125 **Targeting the vINSIST-2 system to the rabbit dentate gyrus for chemically-**
126 **controlled silencing and unsilencing of synaptic transmission**

127 We have developed the next-generation system for virus-delivered silencing of synaptic
128 transmission with a destabilized TeTxLC (dsTeTxLC; vINSIST-2) consisting in three
129 recombinant adeno-associated viruses (rAAVs): virus-1 (rAAV- P_{hSYN} -rtTA), virus-2
130 (pAAV- P_{tet} bi-dsTeTxLC), and virus-3 (pAAV- P_{hSYN} -tdTOM). The destabilized tetanus
131 toxin light chain (dsTeTxLC) has a half-life of ~ 5 minutes (manuscript in preparation).

132 The reverse tetracycline transactivator (rtTA) expressed by the human synapsin
133 promoter (P_{hSYN}) is doxycycline (Dox) dependent. In the presence of Dox, the rtTA/Dox
134 complex binds to the P_{tet} bi to express dsTeTxLC, whereas without Dox, P_{tet} bi is switched-
135 off, and dsTeTxLC expression subsides back to the baseline level (**Fig. 1a** left panel).
136 The dsTeTxLC is a zinc-dependent protease that selectively cleaves the synaptic vesicle
137 protein synaptobrevin-2, so that the depleted synaptic vesicles are unable to perform
138 calcium-dependent neurotransmitter release. The dsTeTxLC thus blocks synaptic
139 transmission (**Fig.1a** right panel).

140 We stereotaxically injected the viral cocktail into the rabbit DG and started the trace
141 eyeblink conditioning experiments three weeks later (**Fig. 1b,c**). With the rtTA system,
142 gene expression can be fully induced with a single intraperitoneal Dox injection already
143 after 24 hours²⁵, and expression subsides to baseline levels within 10 days²⁶. We used a
144 tracer virus expressing tdTOMATO (tdTOM), a red fluorescent protein, under the control
145 of the P_{hSYN} , to validate the targeting of the rabbit DG cells (**Fig. 1d**).

146

147 **Expression of dsTeTxLC in behaving rabbits evokes a reversible loss of acquired** 148 **memories**

149 As detailed in the Methods section, rabbits were prepared for the hippocampal-dependent
150 trace conditioning paradigm in which a tone is presented as a conditioned stimulus (CS)
151 and an air puff as an unconditioned stimulus (US) (**Fig. 1d**).

152 To determine the presence of conditioned eyelid responses, animals were
153 implanted with a bipolar electrode in the upper eyelid to record its electromyographic
154 (EMG) activity (**Fig. 1d, 2b, and 3b**). To record conditionally evoked changes in synaptic
155 strength, the same animals were also implanted with a bipolar stimulating electrode in the
156 perforant pathway and with a tetrode for recording in the ipsilateral CA3 area (**Fig. 1d**).
157 During the same surgical step, the rabbits were stereotaxically injected into the DG with

158 the vINSIST-2 system **Fig. 1d, right**), that allowed specific expression of rAAV encoded
159 genes in granule cells as visualized by dtTOM.

160 Eight days after the surgery and stereotactic injection, the animals have been
161 subjected to classical eyeblink conditioning using trace conditioning paradigm^{1,21,27,28}.
162 After two habituation sessions during which the CS was presented alone, animals
163 received several sessions with paired conditioned and unconditioned stimuli (CS-US)
164 presentations (**Figs. 1d, 2c, and 3c**). Animals were divided into two groups: the first group
165 was conditioned for 8 days (**Figs. 1d and 2c**), while the second group for 22 days (**Figs.**
166 **1d and 3c**). Animals reached the selected criterion for associative learning (> 70% of
167 conditioned responses/session) by the 4th conditioning session (**Figs. 2c and 3c**).

168 The electrical stimulation of the perforant pathway evoked a field excitatory
169 postsynaptic potential (fEPSP) presenting two successive components corresponding to
170 the monosynaptic activation of the CA3 pyramidal cells and their polysynaptic activation
171 across DG granule cells (**Fig. 2a and 3a**). The acquisition of these conditioned responses
172 was accompanied by a small increase in the slope of the evoked fEPSPs at the DG-CA3
173 synapse (**Fig. 2a,c and Fig. 3a,c**).

174 After six conditioning sessions, animals from the first group (**Fig. 2**) were injected
175 with Dox. Four days later, animals were re-recorded for a recall session (**Fig. 2c**). In this
176 situation, rabbits that received either uni- or bilateral tdTOM/TeTxLC injections (n = 3
177 each) presented a significant (Two-way ANOVA, $P \leq 0.05$) decrease in both the
178 percentage of evoked conditioned responses and on the slopes of the second, long-
179 latency component of the fEPSP evoked at the hippocampal CA3 area by the electrical
180 stimulation of the perforant pathway. In contrast, control animals (n = 3) presented values
181 similar ($P \geq 0.092$) to those reached during the 6th conditioning session (**Fig. 2c**).

182 Since dsTeTxLC was only active for 10 days, we conducted a second recall
183 session 14 days after the Dox injection. Interestingly, by that time, the percentage of
184 conditioned responses and the slope of fEPSPs evoked at the PP-CA3 synapse had
185 reached values similar ($P \geq 0.136$) to those presented by the 6th conditioning session,
186 i.e., the day before the Dox injection (**Figs. 2c**). These results indicated that the transient
187 disconnection and reconnection of DG granule cell mossy axons on hippocampal CA3
188 only affected the acquired memory during the disconnection period.

189

190 **dsTeTxLC expression in behaving rabbits evokes a reversible loss of acquired**
191 **motor abilities**

192 In a second set of experiments (**Fig. 3**), we checked whether the transient disconnection
193 between DG granule cells and CA3 pyramidal cells would affect the normal performance
194 of an already acquired conditioned eyelid response and its effects on the concomitant
195 fEPSPs evoked at the CA3 area by perforant pathway stimulation. Animals in this group
196 were conditioned for 22 days. As shown in **Fig. 3c**, the Dox injection in well-trained
197 animals produced a significant (Two-way ANOVA, $P \leq 0.05$) decrease in the percentage
198 of evoked responses (from the 7th to the 14th conditioning sessions) in those animals
199 ($n=3$) already infected with the dsTeTxLC virus. This decrease in the percentage of
200 conditioned responses was accompanied by a significant (Two-way ANOVA, $P \leq 0.05$)
201 reduction in the slope of the late component of fEPSPs evoked at the PP-CA3 synapse.
202 Interestingly, those deficits were compensated during successive conditioning session:
203 an improvement started with the 15th session (i.e., the 7th session after the Dox injection)
204 and became fully complete, reaching control values, by the 22nd training session (i.e., 14
205 sessions after the injection). These results suggest that the performance of an already
206 acquired motor ability could also be affected by the experimental disconnection of the
207 DG-CA3 synapse, but that this depressing effect was recovered to control values after
208 this synapse was reconnected.

209

210 **The density of vGLUT1 and PSD95 expressing puncta decreases after mossy fiber**
211 **output block with dsTeTxLC.**

212 Dox-dependent inducible silencing of synaptic transmission was performed in the
213 hippocampus's rostral and caudal DG with dsTeTxLC (**Fig. 4a, b**). The dsTeTxLC-
214 assisted silencing of the granule cells' mossy *fiber* projections was labeled along the
215 pathway to the CA3 region (**Fig. 4a, b**). The density of puncta expressing vGLUT1, a
216 presynaptic marker of excitatory buttons, and PSD95, an excitatory synapse postsynaptic
217 marker, were analyzed and compared in layer CA3 of the hippocampus. Animals injected
218 with the dsTeTxLC virus showed a statistically significant decrease in both densities of
219 vGLUT1 expressing puncta (Student's t-test = 2.337; $P = 0.0416$) and PSD95 expressing

220 puncta (Student's t-test = 2.345; $P = 0.041$; **Fig. 4a, b**). Compared to controls, after the
221 injection of the dsTeTxLC virus, there was a decrease of ~30 % in vGLUT1 expressing
222 puncta, which emanate from presynaptic mossy fibers infected with dsTeTxLC virus, and
223 of ~20 % in PSD95 expressing puncta, belonging to the CA# pyramidal cells.

224

225 **Time-lapse imaging of mossy fiber boutons**

226 Mouse entorhino-hippocampal slice cultures were prepared and two sets of viruses were
227 locally injected: DG was targeted with rAAV-P_{hSYN}-EGFP, rAAV-P_{hSYN}-rtTA and rAAV-
228 P_{tet}bi-dsTeTxLC and CA3 with rAAV-P_{hSYN}-tdTOM (Fig. 4d). After two weeks, confocal
229 imaging sessions were performed in CA3 to visualize DG-MF boutons (Fig. 4e).
230 Repetitive baseline imaging showed high stability of EGFP-labeled boutons. After
231 baseline imaging, slices were treated with Dox (1 mg/ml) in the medium to activate
232 dsTeTxLC expression. Even with 6 days under Dox for dsTeTxLC expression, boutons
233 were stably detectable as during the baseline imaging sessions (n = 5; 125 mossy fiber
234 boutons total; in one experiment 2 out of 25 boutons were lost after Dox-induced
235 dsTeTxLC). These results indicate that blocking neurotransmitter release does not induce
236 the loss of boutons and most likely the DG-MFs to CA3 connections remained intact.

237

238

239 **DISCUSSION**

240

241 Exploring the roles of interacting brain circuits has been a significant challenge for modern
242 neuroscience. It is becoming increasingly clear that memory engrams are generated in
243 different brain regions^{18,19}. Each brain area has multiple cell types and connectivity
244 patterns within and between brain regions, and experience constantly modifies these
245 circuits. Notably, active and efficient anterograde and retrograde neuronal signaling
246 between neurons establishes and maintains synaptic connections. This allows memory
247 engrams to be formed across synaptically-connected brain regions, involving different
248 bidirectional mechanisms, such as the release of various factors, endosomal tracking,
249 cytoskeleton dynamics in neuronal compartments²⁹, calcium influx³⁰, neurotrophin
250 factors(s)³¹, nitrogen oxide/carbon monoxide³², 2-arachidonoylglycerol for cannabinoid

251 signaling³³, dopamine transporter trafficking³⁴, and epigenetic³⁵ and gene expression^{36,37}.
252 Inhibition of neuronal activity by hyperpolarization can interfere with numerous
253 biochemical processes³⁰ that, in turn, could disrupt intrinsic³⁸, synaptic³⁹, and homeostatic
254 plasticity⁴⁰, and thus learning and memory processes.

255 In the hippocampus, DG serves as a gateway for the flow of information from EC
256 to the hippocampus. The DG granule cells receive input from the EC and provide
257 information along the mossy fiber pathway to the CA3, which projects to the CA1. There
258 are also direct connections from the EC to CA1 (and to CA3). DG-CA3 circuits are
259 essential for pattern separation^{9,10}, while CA3-CA1 neurons contribute to pattern
260 completion¹¹. Memory engrams are likely formed and maintained along these EC-
261 trisynaptic-subcortical-cortical circuits. It has been suggested that EC inputs to the DG
262 are important for learning but not for recall. On the other hand, direct perforant path EC
263 input to CA3 provides cue-assisted memory recall but is not used for learning¹². Sensory
264 signals during learning activate cell assemblies in the EC that project to the dendrites of
265 DG granule cells (GCs)^{14,15}. It is plausible that concurrent EC input to the DC-GCs
266 dendrites in concert with presynaptic NMDA receptors on mossy fibers (MF)⁴¹ and
267 postsynaptic NMDA receptors in CA3 neurons¹⁷ induce plasticity⁴². CA1 dendritic activity
268 patterns play a crucial role in place field determination⁴³. The complexity of the
269 hippocampus circuits in mapping external and internal synaptic input against the
270 backdrop of intrinsic circuit-driven synaptic activity⁶ is further shaped by the interaction
271 between DG-GC axons projecting to the hilus, where they make synaptic connections
272 with mossy cells (MCs). Different classes of GABAergic DG and CA3 neuron types, such
273 as parvalbumin-positive and somatostatin-positive neurons, bidirectionally control
274 synaptic drive to their project to CA3 and between CA3-CA1 and EC-CA1 circuits⁴⁴, that
275 modulate synaptic plasticity by excitation-inhibition balance⁴⁵. These processes play
276 important roles in generating stable engrams^{46,47} and temporally binding them across
277 brain regions for memory recall⁴⁸⁻⁵⁰. In addition, gap junctions⁵¹ formed in these
278 hippocampal circuits might serve as cellular and network mechanisms for ultrafast
279 communication between cells for assembling memories, their storage, and recall¹².

280 There are two widely used technologies for inhibiting neuronal activity: DREADD²⁰
281 activated by CNO) and microbial opsins proteins such as halorhodopsin activated by

282 photostimulation. Both methods inhibit target neurons by hyperpolarizing them. Previous
283 studies showed that after learning, optogenetic inhibition of the DG impaired the
284 expression of initially encoded memory, demonstrating necessity²², whereas optogenetic
285 activation of learning-tagged DG neurons induced memory recall, indicating sufficiency⁵².
286 Whether memory trace remained stable in the hippocampus circuitry or moved to the
287 cortex over time is at the beginning stage of our understanding^{53,54}. Interestingly, it was
288 reported that virus-delivered DREADD/CNO-mediated inhibition of the DG after trace
289 eyeblink conditioning erased the memory engrams along the EC-trisynaptic circuits²⁰. It
290 is, however, possible that memory engrams were suppressed or had become latent by
291 prolonged hyperpolarization^{55,56}. Notably, the optogenetic-induced hyperpolarization of
292 DG neurons was applied for a few minutes²², while DREADD-induced hyperpolarizing
293 lasted for at least a few hours^{21,23}.

294 We suggest that DREADD/CNO-induced hyperpolarization was sufficient to erase
295 the synaptic memory engrams from the DG-CA3 synapse in both the anterograde
296 direction (presynaptic DG to postsynaptic CA3) and retrograde direction (postsynaptic DG
297 to presynaptic EC), thus erasing memory engrams along the EC – hippocampus
298 trisynaptic circuits. Transient hyperpolarization by optogenetic (by light illumination) was
299 instead short enough to retain the engram, which led to memory retrieval when light
300 illumination was switched-off. We suggest that these two opposite findings were likely due
301 to the different technologies applied.

302 To clarify the issue, we hypothesized that if DG synaptic output is silenced
303 selectively, without hyperpolarizing neurons, by blocking presynaptic neurotransmitter
304 release, the synaptic memory engram would not be erased. In this way, memory retrieval
305 would be re-established after the un-silencing of synaptic transmission. To selectively
306 block DG output, we developed and applied the next-generation advanced chemically-
307 controlled technology for virus-delivered Inducible Silencing of Synaptic Transmission
308 version-2 (vINSIST-2) (**Fig. 1**). Previous studies have shown that TeTxLC-mediated DG-
309 MF silencing of synaptic output leads to normal MF excitability, normal MF projection
310 throughout CA3 stratum lucidum, unaltered ultrastructural MF terminals, unaltered
311 electrophysiological characteristics, and normal LTP of perforant path inputs⁵⁷. This

312 makes our TeTxLC-based vINSIST-2 system highly valuable to investigate the selective
313 role of DG output without hyperpolarizing neurons.

314 To explore this possibility, we used the trace eyeblink conditioning paradigm, which
315 is considered a prototypic example of declarative memory, and we used rabbits for our
316 experiments because it is a well-established animal model for trace eyeblink conditioning
317 with air-puff as an US (without the need to perform electrical stimulation to the eyelid as
318 commonly done with mice, which can activate additional somatosensory circuits). The
319 rabbits were trained in trace eyeblink conditioning consisting of a tone followed by an air
320 puff to the eye's cornea with a 500-ms temporal interval. This training resulted in robust
321 memory formation for the conditioned eyeblink response to the tone when presented
322 alone. We used the vINSIST-2 to target the rabbit DG to selectively block synaptic
323 transmission of the DG-MF output. Three weeks after vINSIST-2 delivery to the DG, we
324 performed conditioning. *In vivo* electrophysiology recordings were carried out at the DG-
325 CA3 synapse to measure network-level development of synaptic strength over the
326 conditioning trials while also measuring conditioned responses (**Fig. 2, Fig. 3**). Our results
327 showed that synaptic connections between the DG-MF and CA3 were strengthened
328 during conditioning following increased conditioned responses. Silencing of synaptic
329 transmission of the DG-MF over days by Dox-induced vINSIST-2 expression reduced
330 conditioned responses, and the synaptic strengths between DG-MF and CA3 neurons
331 collapsed. However, un-silencing DG-MF synaptic transmission by removing Dox for two
332 weeks, mainly due to slow Dox clearance from the brain²⁶, restored conditioned
333 responses and the synaptic strengths between DG-MF and CA3 (**Fig. 2**). Similar results
334 were found during over-conditioning, where the conditioning sessions continued after
335 Dox-induced vINSIST-2 expression during the silencing session, and learning level and
336 synaptic activity were recovered entirely two weeks after the Dox injection (**Fig. 3**). Our
337 results show that despite of animals being "overtrained", no increase in the number of
338 conditioned responses was observed during prolonged silencing of the synaptic
339 transmission, and the previously formed memory trace was not erased. The DG-MF
340 output was therefore required for memory retrieval, and furthermore, no new engrams
341 could overtake during the silencing period.

342 In support of our hypothesis, we found that upon silencing synaptic transmission,
343 vGlut and PSD95 puncta corresponding to the DG-MF boutons and CA3 spines were
344 significantly reduced (**Fig. 4a,b**). In keeping with this hypothesis is the finding that activity-
345 dependent recruitment of synaptic proteins for efficient synaptic transmission plays a
346 pivotal role in preserving and stabilizing the synaptic memory engram(s)^{59,60}. Reduction
347 of vGlut and PSD95 at the DG-CA3 synapse, as detected in our study by silencing of
348 synaptic transmission, functionally disconnected the synaptic engram, which upon un-
349 silencing the engram was recovered, possibly by activity-dependent recruited vGlut and
350 PSD95 back to the synaptic connections.

351 To investigate whether vINSIST-2 assisted silencing of DG output induces the loss
352 of MF boutons in mouse entorhino-hippocampal slice cultures, we used vINSIST-2 to the
353 DG and virus-delivered green fluorescence protein (EGFP) and tdTOM to DG and CA3,
354 respectively. We performed time-lapse repetitive confocal imaging on slice cultures over
355 several days to establish stability of DG-MF boutons projecting to the CA3 region of the
356 hippocampus. We found that even after 6 days of Dox-induced dsTeTxLC-mediated
357 silencing of synaptic transmission DG-MF boutons remained stable (**Fig. 4c-g**),
358 consistent with previous findings^{57,58}.

359 We suggest that, unlike the DREADD-mediated inhibition of DG, that impaired
360 memory expression, possibly by erasing the EC-DG and DG-CA3 synaptic engrams
361 along the EC-trisynaptic circuit, the silencing of DG-MF output by our vINSIST-2
362 (dsTeTxLC) technology, would keep the synaptic engram undisturbed and intact for
363 memory retrieval after un-silencing of synaptic transmission. The differences in the results
364 are likely due to the genetic approaches used; the DREADD system hyperpolarizes
365 neurons, blocking anterograde and retrograde signaling, while dsTeTxLC only blocked
366 presynaptic neurotransmitter release by cleavage of vesicle-containing synaptobrevin-2
367 for evoked synaptic transmission. Thus, in the previous work with DREADD-mediated DG
368 inhibition²¹, the memory trace that develops in the DG possibly functionally disconnected
369 between the presynaptic neurons providing input to the DG and the postsynaptic neurons
370 that receive information from the DG. With such polysynaptic functional disconnection,
371 we suggest that synaptic memory engrams previously formed along the EC-DG-CA3
372 pathway were erased. However, with vINSIST-2 (dsTeTxLC)-mediated presynaptic

373 silencing of the DG-MF output, the memory engram remained undisturbed and intact for
374 retrieval after un-silencing of synaptic transmission.

375 It is important to note that synaptic networks are equipped with mechanisms that
376 can recruit a repertoire of synaptic connections and weights for flexibility and efficient
377 formation of sensory representation and memory retrieval^{61,62}. In light of previous
378 findings^{21,22}, our current work suggests that memory engrams are synaptically printed
379 from one region to the next and distributed throughout the brain. It seems quite plausible
380 that destabilization of synaptic connections after silencing and subsequent un-silencing
381 of synaptic transmission would flexibly establish re-organized synaptic connectivity and
382 synaptic weights^{62,63}. Based on dynamically activated cell assemblies⁶⁴ in EC, DG, CA3,
383 CA1, and cortical regions, and synaptically-connected subcortical and cortical areas, and
384 previous findings^{18,19}, it seems likely that memory engrams are distributed across the
385 different brain regions.

386 All methods are helpful, but our interpretation of experiments has to carefully take
387 into account the mechanisms and differences across these procedures in order to better
388 understand how biology and the brain work. The discoveries made with the application
389 and DREADD and optogenetics and our vINSIST-2 technologies to investigate the role
390 of DG in memory retrieval have provided significant insight based on the circuit
391 manipulation schemes^{21,22,24}. A comprehensive understanding of the EC-trisynaptic and
392 subcortical and cortical circuits would continue to demand the development of advanced
393 genetic tools for slice electrophysiology and *in vivo* imaging, recordings, and activity
394 manipulation of different cell types to dissect their role and gain deeper insight into the
395 learning and memory processes.

396

397

398 **MATERIALS AND METHODS**

399

400 **Animals (Ethical statement)**

401 Experiments were carried out on adult male rabbits (New Zealand white albino) weighing
402 2.6-3.1 kg on arrival, obtained from an authorized supplier (Isoquimen, S.L., Barcelona,
403 Spain). Animals were housed in individual cages for the experiment and kept on a 12/12

404 h light/dark cycle with constant ambient temperature (21 ± 1 °C) and humidity ($50 \pm 7\%$).
405 Food and water were available *ad libitum*. All experimental procedures followed the
406 guidelines of the European Union Council (2010/276:33-79/EU) and Spanish (BOE
407 34:11370-421, 2013) regulations for using laboratory animals in chronic experiments. The
408 local University Ethics Committee also approved experimental protocols.

409

410 **AAV plasmids**

411 We developed the next-generation genetic technology for virus-delivered inducible
412 silencing of synaptic transmission version-2 (INSIST-2). Two plasmid sets were
413 generated, and recombinant adeno-associated viruses (rAAVs) were prepared with the
414 tetracycline-controlled genetic switches: Set-1 included rAAV-**P_{hSYN}**-tdTOMvirus,
415 meanwhile, Set-2 included the rAAV-**P_{hSYN}**-rtTA, rAAV-**P_{tet}bi**-dsTeTxLC and rAAV-**P_{hSYN}**-
416 tdTOM viruses. The destabilized tetanus toxin (dsTeTxLC) has a very short half-life time.
417 The vINSIST-2 system will be described in a separate publication.

418

419 **Protein extraction and Western blot**

420 Rat organotypic slices infected with either rAAV-**P_{tet}bi**-dsTeTxLC and rAAV-**P_{hSYN}**-rtTA
421 were harvested in cold lysis buffer (50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 7.6; 5mM MgCl₂; 130 mM NaCl;
422 10mM KCl; 1% Triton X-100; 5% Glycerin) 14 days after virus infection and homogenized
423 by sonication. Lysis buffer was supplemented with a protease inhibitor cocktail
424 (Complete™; Roche). Protein concentration was determined by Bradford assay. 15 µg of
425 the protein lysates from both rAAV infected and uninfected rat hippocampus organotypic
426 slices were separated by SDS-Page gel (15 % separating and 6% stacking gels) and
427 transferred onto nitrocellulose membranes. Western blots were probed with the following
428 primary antibodies: synaptobrevin-2 (1:1000, Abcam) and polyclonal mouse anti- β-
429 tubulin (1:1000, Millipore). The secondary antibodies used were; horseradish peroxidase-
430 linked anti-rabbit, anti-goat, or anti-mouse (1:15000, Vector Laboratories, Peterborough,
431 UK). Western blots were detected by an enhanced chemiluminescence kit (ECL kit,
432 Amersham Pharmacia Biotech, Freiburg, Germany).

433

434 **Electrophysiology in brain slices**

435 Three weeks old were injected the vINSIST system to the DG, and Dox activation was
436 performed for 48 hours by single intraperitoneal Dox injection. We prepared and recorded
437 brain slices from 6 weeks old C57BL/6 mice (Charles River; Sulzfeld, Germany), as
438 described before⁶⁵. All experimental procedures were performed according to the animal
439 welfare guidelines of the Max Planck Society. Briefly, the mice were decapitated under
440 deep isoflurane anesthesia, and the brains were rapidly dissected, and combined
441 entorhinal cortex–hippocampus transverse slices (400 μm) were cut with a vibroslicer
442 (VT1000S, Leica) in dissection buffer (4 °C) containing (in mM): 212.7 sucrose, 5 KCl,
443 1.25 NaH_2PO_4 , 10 MgCl_2 , 0.5 CaCl_2 , 26 NaHCO_3 , 10 dextrose. The slices were then
444 stored in normal artificial cerebrospinal fluid (ACSF) for at least 1.5 hours before
445 recording. Slices were transferred, as needed, to a submerged recording chamber, where
446 they were perfused with ACSF (2 ml/min). Both cutting and ACSF solutions were
447 saturated with 95% O_2 /5% CO_2 (pH 7.4). Normal ACSF was similar to the dissection
448 buffer except that sucrose was replaced by 119 mM NaCl, MgCl_2 was lowered to 1 mM,
449 and CaCl_2 was raised to 2 mM. Extracellular responses from area CA3b to DG stimulation
450 were filtered at 2 kHz and digitized at 10 kHz using an EPC-10 amplifier controlled by
451 Patchmaster (HekaElektronik, Lambrecht, Germany). We used microelectrodes of 8–12
452 $\text{M}\Omega$ filled with normal ACSF for stimulation and recording. To evoke synaptic responses
453 in CA3, electrical stimulation (pulse duration 0.1 ms; $\leq 80 \mu\text{A}$) was delivered at 0.05 Hz
454 over the molecular layer of the DG. We characterized the input/output curves by evoking
455 ten responses at each stimulus intensity. All recordings were performed at $30 \pm 1^\circ\text{C}$. The
456 digitized extracellular recordings were exported and analyzed with a program written in
457 MATLAB R2014a (MathWorks, Inc.). This program computes averages of ten field
458 responses evoked at each stimulation intensity and extracts the initial slope of the
459 descending negative limb of the averaged field potential (in mV/ms). Results are reported
460 as \pm s.e.m. Statistical significance was set at $P < 0.05$.

461

462 **Stereotactic virus injection with vINSIST-2**

463 Here we applied an advanced next-generation technology for virus-delivered **I**nducible
464 **S**ilencing of **S**ynaptic **T**ransmission or vINSIST-2. The dorsal DG of rabbits was injected
465 with a solution consisting of three viruses (0.75 μL in 9/18 different points). A single

466 intraperitoneal Dox injection in rabbits allows for neuron-specific dsTeTxLC expression,
467 which cleavages synaptobrevin-2, impairing synaptic transmission. As brain Dox
468 concentration subsides, dsTeTxLC expression is also reduced in parallel, restoring
469 normal synaptic transmission. Experimental groups: in the first series of experiments (n
470 = 3 animals per group; **Fig. 2**), animals received two habituation (days 1-2) and six
471 conditioning (days 3-8) sessions. Afterward, they received two recall sessions (days 12
472 and 22). In the second series of experiments (n = 3 animals per group; **Fig. 3**), animals
473 received two habituation and 20 conditioning sessions. In both cases, animals received
474 Dox injection 30 min before the 9th session. As brain Dox concentration subsides,
475 dsTeTxLC expression is also reduced in parallel, restoring normal synaptic transmission.

476 In all the animals, the dsTeTxLC expression was activated by doxycycline (Dox)
477 injection after six days of conditioning (**Figs. 2 and 3**). In the first series of experiments
478 (**Fig. 2**), two recall sessions were carried out 4 and 14 days after doxycycline injections.
479 In the second series of experiments (**Fig. 3**), animals were conditioned for 14 additional
480 days after doxycycline injections.

481 At the end of the experiments, animals were deeply anesthetized with sodium
482 pentobarbital (50 mg/kg, i.p.) and perfused transcardially with saline and 4%
483 paraformaldehyde. To determine the final location of recording and stimulation sites, the
484 brains were removed from animals and cut into slices (50 μ m). The relevant brain areas
485 were processed for Nissl (toluidine blue) staining.

486

487 **Animal handling and stereotactic virus injection in the rabbit brain**

488 To accomplish full DG targeting, we injected 9 points of the dentate gyrus for unilateral
489 infected animals, and 18 points for bilateral infected animals using the corresponding set
490 of viruses. For this purpose, the needed number of points were drilled in the skull of the
491 animal during the surgery for electrode implantation, and the cocktail of the virus was
492 delivered using a glass pipette connected to a plastic tube and, finally, to a 50 ml syringe
493 that was used as an impulsion system. A total volume of 0.75 μ l was injected at each of
494 the selected sites at a speed of 0.15 μ l/min. The stereotaxic coordinates used to spread
495 the infection over the whole dentate gyrus are shown in **Table 1**.

496

497 **Classical conditioning of eyelid responses and fEPSP recordings in behaving**
498 **rabbits**

499 Experiments were carried out on adult male rabbits (New Zealand white albino) weighing
500 2.6-3.1 kg on arrival, obtained from an authorized supplier (Isoquimen, S.L., Barcelona,
501 Spain). Animals were housed in individual cages for the experiment and kept on a 12/12
502 h light/dark cycle with constant ambient temperature (21 ± 1 °C) and humidity ($50 \pm 7\%$).
503 Food and water were available *ad libitum*. All experimental procedures followed the
504 guidelines of the European Union Council (2010/276:33-79/EU) and Spanish (BOE
505 34:11370-421, 2013) regulations for using laboratory animals in chronic experiments. The
506 local University Ethics Committee also approved experimental protocols.

507 Classical conditioning was carried out using a trace paradigm. Animals were
508 presented with a tone as a conditioned stimulus and an air puff as an unconditioned
509 stimulus. Conditioned responses were determined from the electromyographic (EMG)
510 activity of the orbicularis oculi muscle (**Figs. 1d, 2b, and 3b**). Animals were prepared for
511 the chronic recording of fEPSPs evoked at the CA3 area of the dorsal hippocampus by
512 the electrical stimulation of the ipsilateral perforant pathway and for the classical
513 conditioning of eyelid responses. For this, they were anesthetized with a ketamine-
514 xylazine cocktail (Ketaminol, 50 mg/mL; Rompun, 20 mg/mL; and atropine sulfate, 0.5
515 mg/kg) and implanted with bipolar stimulating electrodes in the perforant pathway and
516 with single tetrode recording electrodes (homemade tungsten electrode with 4 tips
517 separated by 0.2 mm) in the hippocampal CA3 area. Stimulating and recording electrodes
518 were made from 50 μ m, Teflon-coated tungsten wire (Advent Research Materials Ltd.,
519 Eynsham, England). The impedance of recording electrodes was always ≤ 1 M Ω . The
520 final position of hippocampal stimulating and recording electrodes was determined under
521 recording procedures until a reliable monosynaptic field EPSP was identified²⁶. During
522 the same surgical step, animals have injected uni- or bilaterally (n = 3 per group) in the
523 dorsal DG (red circles in **Fig. 1d**) with the viral Set-2. Additional control animals (n = 3 per
524 group) were injected with the viral Set-1. All the animals were also implanted with
525 recording bipolar hook electrodes in the left orbicularis oculi muscle to record its EMG
526 activity. These electrodes were made from Teflon-coated stainless-steel wire (A-M
527 Systems, WA, USA) with an external diameter of 50 μ m. A silver electrode (1 mm in

528 diameter) was attached to the skull (occipital bone) as a ground. All wire connections
529 were covered with cyanoacrylate glue, and the whole system was attached to the skull
530 with 3 small screws fastened and cemented with an acrylic resin to the bone^{28,68}.
531 Terminals of hippocampal stimulating and recording, EMG, and ground electrodes were
532 soldered to nine-pin sockets.

533 Conditioning consisted of two habituation and 6 conditioning sessions in the case
534 of the recall protocol and 20 conditioning sessions in the case of the over-conditioning
535 protocol. The trace conditioning paradigm consisted of a 100 ms, 600 Hz, 85 dB tone
536 followed 300 ms after CS onset by a 100 ms, 3 kg/cm² air puff aimed at the left cornea;
537 thus, a trace interval of 200 ms was left between CS end and US onset. Conditioning
538 sessions consisted of 66 trials (6 series of 11 trials each) separated randomly by intervals
539 of 50-70 s. Of the 66 test trials, six were presented in the CS alone. A complete
540 conditioning session lasted for ~ 1 h. The CS was presented alone during habituation
541 sessions for the same number of blocks/sessions and trials/blocks. As a criterion, we
542 considered a "CR" the presence, during the CS-US interval, of EMG activity lasting > 10
543 ms and initiated > 50 ms after CS onset. In addition, the integrated EMG activity recorded
544 during the CS-US interval had to be at least 1.2 times greater than the integrated EMG
545 recorded immediately before the CS presentation. As a criterion for learning, animals
546 should evoke > 70% CRs by the 10th conditioning session^{6,27,28,66}.

547

548 **Recording and stimulation**

549 Two weeks after surgery, rabbits were placed in a Perspex box designed to limit the
550 subject's movements^{6,27,28,66}. The box was placed on the recording table and covered by
551 a black cloth. The recording room was softly illuminated, and a 60-dB background white
552 noise was switched-on during the experiments. The EMG activity of the selected muscle
553 was recorded using Grass P511 differential amplifiers with a bandwidth of 0.1 Hz to 10
554 kHz (Grass-Telefactor, West Warwick, RI, USA). The fEPSPs were recorded with a 16-
555 channel extracellular differential AC amplifier (Model 3500, A-M Systems, Sequim, WA,
556 USA) provided with a head-stage interface adapter. Air puffs aimed at the left cornea were
557 applied through the opening of a plastic pipette (3 mm in diameter) attached to a metal
558 holder fixed to the animal's nine-pin socket (Dual-channel air-puff device, Biomedical

559 Engineering Co.). Tones were applied from a loudspeaker 80 cm below the animal's head.
560 Electrical stimulation of the selected sites was achieved with a CS-220 stimulator across
561 an ISU-220 isolation unit (Cibertec, Madrid, Spain). Single (cathodal, square, 50 ms, < 1
562 mA pulses) or paired (40 of an inter-pulse interval) stimuli were programmed.

563

564 **Fluorescence Immunohistochemistry**

565 Five rabbits were used for the control group, and 7 rabbits were used to analyze the
566 puncta density after injected dsTeTxLC expression. Brains for fluorescence
567 immunohistochemistry were cryoprotected with 30% sucrose in PB. Then coronal
568 sections (50 μ m) were obtained with a sliding freezing microtome (Leica SM2000R) and
569 stored at -20°C in 30% glycerol and 30% ethylene glycol in PB until used. Brain slices
570 were processed "free-floating" for immunohistochemistry, and all of the sections studied
571 passed through all procedures simultaneously to minimize any difference from
572 immunohistochemical staining itself. To analyze the density of the vesicular glutamate
573 transporter 1 (vGLUT1) expressing puncta, a presynaptic marker of excitatory boutons,
574 and the postsynaptic density 95 (PSD95) representing puncta, an excitatory synapse
575 postsynaptic marker^{67,68}, we have performed immunohistochemistry using primary
576 antibodies against VGLUT1 or PSD95 (Millipore Iberica S.A.U, Madrid, Spain). Briefly,
577 sections were incubated for 1 h with 5% normal donkey serum (NDS) (AbDSerotec,
578 MorphoSys, Kidlington, UK) in phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) with 0.2% Triton-X-100
579 (Sigma-Aldrich, St. Louis, MO, USA) and then they were incubated overnight at room
580 temperature with mouse monoclonal IgG anti-VGLUT1 (1:1000) or mouse monoclonal
581 IgG anti-PSD95 (1:700) with PBS containing 0.2% Triton-X-100 and 3% NDS. On the
582 second day, sections were washed and incubated for 1 h with anti-mouse IgG secondary
583 antibodies generated in donkeys and conjugated with Alexa 488 and Alexa 647 (1:200;
584 Millipore Iberica S.A.U, Madrid, Spain) in PBS containing 0.2% Triton-X-100 and 3%
585 NDS. Finally, sections were mounted on slides and cover-slipped using Prolong Gold
586 antifade reagent fluorescent mounting medium (Millipore Iberica S.A.U, Madrid, Spain).

587

588 **Analysis of vGLUT1 and PSD95 expressing puncta**

589 All slides were coded before analysis, and the codes were not broken until the experiment
590 was finished. The density of vGLUT1 and PSD95 expressing puncta were analyzed and
591 compared in the CA3 region of the hippocampus. Sections from the same rostral-caudal
592 level were examined under a confocal microscope (Leica TCS SPE). Z-series of optical
593 sections (0.5 μm apart) were obtained using sequential scanning mode and processed
594 with Image J software. Photographs were taken at 63X magnification. The values of
595 acquisition settings, such as the laser intensity percentage, gain, offset, and resolution,
596 were identical for each stack taken from the same level. All of them had a similar time of
597 exposure to the confocal laser. Subsequently, confocal images from similar Z-position in
598 which the same level of antibody penetrability was observed were chosen from each
599 stack, and five random sampling with size $16 \times 16 \mu\text{m}$ were collected to analyze to avoid
600 somas or blood vessels. Then, the background fluorescence of each image was
601 subtracted. Due to the density and proximity of puncta, these were divided into three size
602 groups of pixels; the group with the biggest size was not considered since it could only
603 represent the same fibrillar processes. Then, images were normalized, and the threshold
604 set and puncta were counted automatically using ImageJ software. Means were
605 determined for each experimental group, and the data were subjected to an unpaired
606 Student's *t*-test.

607

608 **Repetitive imaging of dentate gyrus mossy fiber boutons**

609 Mouse entorhinal-hippocampal slice cultures were prepared and imaged as described
610 before^{70,71}. At day 3 *in vitro* rAAV-P_{hSYN}-EGFP, rAAV-P_{hSYN}-rtTA and rAAV-P_{tet}-bi-
611 dsTeTxLC were locally injected in to DG and rAAV-P_{hSYN}-tdTOM into CA3 using glass
612 pipettes. Two weeks later, i.e., 18-22 days *in vitro*, slice cultures on the filter inserts
613 (Millipore, Germany) were transferred to a petri dish containing preheated (35 °C) imaging
614 medium (NaCl 129 mM, KCl 4 mM, MgCl₂ 1 mM, CaCl₂ 2 mM, glucose 4.2 mM, HEPES
615 10 mM, Trolox 0.1 mM, streptomycin 0.1 mg/ml, penicillin 100 U/ml; pH 7.4; with sucrose,
616 osmolarity was adjusted that matched the osmolarity of the culture medium). Filter inserts
617 were secured by a custom-made titanium ring. The cultures were viewed with an upright
618 Zeiss LSM Pascal confocal microscope. A 10x water immersion objective (0.3 NA, Zeiss,
619 Germany) was used to visualize the culture at a low magnification to identify individual

620 CA3 pyramidal neurons and mossy fibers. Then a 63x water immersion objective (0.95
621 NA; Zeiss, Germany) was used to image mossy fiber synaptic boutons. CA3 pyramidal
622 neurons served as an orientation for re-identification across multiple imaging sessions.
623 Up to 25 images were recorded per stack with an ideal Nyquist rate using the same
624 imaging procedure and settings at the microscope for all consecutive time points. For
625 analysis, 25 mossy fiber boutons were identified in in the middle of each confocal image
626 stack and followed over time in max. intensity 2D-projections of the following imaging time
627 points.

628

629 **Data collection and analysis**

630 The fEPSPs, the unrectified EMG activity of the recorded muscles, and 1-V rectangular
631 pulses corresponding to CS, US, and electrical stimuli presented during the different
632 experimental situations were acquired online through an 8-channel analog-to-digital
633 converter (CED 1401-plus, CED, Cambridge, UK), and transferred to a computer for
634 quantitative off-line analysis. Data were sampled at 8000 Hz (for fEPSP recordings) or
635 4000 Hz (for EMG recordings), with an amplitude resolution of 12 bits. Computer
636 programs (Spike2 and SIGAVG from CED) were used to analyze field potentials and EMG
637 activities. These programs allowed the quantification of the onset latency and area (mV's)
638 of the rectified EMG activity of the orbicularis oculi muscle with the aid of cursors. Field
639 synaptic potentials (in mV) collected from the same session ($n = 66$) and animal were
640 averaged, and the mean value of the slope (in mV/s) was determined for the rise time
641 (i.e., the period of the slope between the initial 10% and the final 10% of the evoked field
642 potential). Statistical analyses were performed using the Sigma Plot 11.0 package (Sigma
643 Plot, San Jose, CA, USA) for a statistical significance level of $P = 0.05$. Unless otherwise
644 indicated, mean values were calculated from 15 electrodes collected from three animals.
645 Mean values are followed by their standard error (SEM). Collected data were analyzed
646 using the one-way or two-way ANOVA test, with time or session as a repeated measure
647 and contrast and non-parametric analysis when appropriate. Repeated-measures
648 ANOVA allowed for checking the statistical differences of the same group across
649 sessions. The Student t-test was used when necessary.

650

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953

954 **AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS**

955 M.T.H. and J.M.D.-G. conceived and supervised the project; M.T.H. developed the vINSIST-2 technology;
956 G.K.D., I.B., M.T. and M.T.H. characterized vINSIST-2; A.C.G. performed in vivo ePhys and behavior;
957 A.C.G., A.G. and J.M.D.-G contributed in the analysis of electrophysiology and behavior data; M.A.G.C.
958 contributed in performing expression mapping, vGlut and PSD95 imaging and data analysis on fixed rabbit
959 brains; A.V. performed confocal imaging of DG-MF boutons and data analysis; M.E.L. and R.S. provided
960 crucial scientific input; J.M.D.-G. and M.T.H. prepared the manuscript with input from M.T., I.B., A.C.G.,
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974 **COMPETING INTERESTS**

975 The authors declare no competing interests.

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978 **ADDITIONAL INFORMATION**

979

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987 **FIGURE LEGENDS**

988

989 **Fig. 1 A diagrammatic representation of the experimental design for classical eyeblink**
990 **conditioning and virus-delivered silencing of synaptic transmission.**

991 **a** Schematic diagram of tetracycline-controlled genetic switches for dsTeTxLC expression to
992 selectively cleave a key synaptic vesicle protein, synaptobrevin-2. Virus-1 is equipped with the
993 human synapsin promoter (P_{hSYN}) to express the reverse tetracycline transactivator (rtTA), virus-
994 2 has a bidirectional tetracycline promoter to express a destabilized tetanus toxin light chain
995 (dsTeTxLC) with a short half-life time. Only in the presence of Dox is P_{tet} biactivated to express
996 dsTeTxLC. For validating targeting of gene expression in the brain, the virus-3 was used that
997 expresses tdTomato under control of P_{hSYN} . **b** Levels of synaptobrevin-2 were determined by a
998 Western blot for control (without dsTeTxLC, un-infected) and with dsTeTxLC (infected) neurons
999 (β -tubulin as a control) to validate dsTeTxLC cleavage of synaptobrevin-2. **c** A schematic view
1000 Drawing of rAAVs injected into a mouse (left panel) and a schematic of an hippocampal slice for
1001 *in vitro* experiments with stimulating electrode in dentate gyrus (DG) and the recording electrode
1002 in CA3 (insert inside the input/output curve). The input/output curves compare the slopes of
1003 averaged field potentials (10 repetitions/intensity) with increasing stimulation intensities from
1004 control (in black) and TeTxLC-infected (in red) slices (RM-ANOVA test, $P < 0.001$). **d** A schematic
1005 view of the electrode placements in two regions in the dorsal hippocampus with a stimulation
1006 electrode (\bullet) in the perforant path (PP) to the dentate gyrus (DG) and the recording electrodes in
1007 CA3 (O). Rabbits were injected in the DG with a cocktail solution consisting of three viruses in 7
1008 different sites as indicated (\bullet). LV = left ventricle. **e** The rAAV cocktail was injected into the rabbit
1009 DG and precisely targeting was validated by tdTomato expression (red fluorescence). **f** Schematic
1010 of view the cortical-hippocampal trisynaptic circuit depicting the different pathways including the
1011 PP (EC to DG) and the SC (CA3 to CA1) pathways.

1012

1013 **Fig. 2 Effects on recall memories and on the underlying hippocampal changes in synaptic**

1014 **strength of dsTeTxLC activation by Dox.** **a** Representative example of fEPSPs (averaged 5
1015 times) evoked at the CA3 area by electrical stimulation of the perforant pathway (PP St.) during
1016 the CS-US interval (200 ms after CS presentation). **b** Evolution of conditioned eyeblink responses
1017 evoked in control (white circles), and in unilaterally (gray circles) or bilaterally (black circles)
1018 injected animals with Dox. Note the absence of conditioned responses during the period of
1019 dsTeTxLC activation (2) as compared with previous (1) and later (3) recording sessions. **c** From
1020 top to bottom is illustrated the experimental design, a quantitative analysis of the evolution of the

1021 second component of fEPSPs evoked at the CA3 area by electrical stimulation of the PP, and
1022 learning evolution across habituation (days 1-2), conditioning (days 3-8), and recall (days 12 and
1023 22) sessions. Representative examples of recorded fEPSPs and conditioned eyelid responses
1024 are illustrated in **a** and **b**, respectively. Note that dsTeTxLC activation prevented the proper
1025 expression of the expected changes in synaptic strength and learning rates. * (control vs.
1026 unilateral dsTeTxLC inj.), • (control vs. bilateral dsTeTxLC inj.), $P \leq 0.05$.

1027
1028 **Fig. 3 Effects on classical conditioning and on the underlying hippocampal changes in**
1029 **synaptic strength of dsTeTxLC activation by Dox.** **a** Representative example of fEPSPs
1030 (averaged 5 times) evoked at the PP-CA3 synapse at the CS-US interval (200 ms after CS
1031 presentation) during conditioning. **b** Evolution of conditioned eyeblink responses evoked in control
1032 (white circles) and in bilaterally (black circles) injected animals with Dox. Note the absence and/or
1033 decrease in the amplitude of conditioned responses during the period of dsTeTxLC activation (2,
1034 3) as compared with previous (1) and later (4) recording sessions. **c** From top to bottom is
1035 illustrated the experimental design, a quantitative analysis of the evolution of the second
1036 component of fEPSPs evoked at the CA3 area by the electrical stimulation of the PP, and learning
1037 evolution across habituation (days 1-2), conditioning (days 3-22) sessions. Representative
1038 examples of recorded fEPSPs and conditioned eyelid responses are illustrated in **a** and **b**,
1039 respectively. Note that dsTeTxLC activation prevented the proper expression of the expected
1040 changes in synaptic strength and learning rates. *, $P \leq 0.05$.

1041
1042 **Figure 4 | TeTxLC changes in vGLUT1 and PSD 95 expressing puncta and stability of**
1043 **mossy fiber boutons.** **(a)** Confocal imaging of vGLUT1 and PSD95 expressing puncta in DG
1044 mossy fibers and CA3 neuropil of control and dsTeTxLC rabbit brain slices. Note the dsTeTxLC
1045 labeled puncta in all four cases. Scale bar: 25 μm . **(b)** Graphs representing the changes in the
1046 density of vGLUT1 (Student's t-test 2.337; $P = 0.0416$) and PSD95 (Student's t-test = 2.345; $P =$
1047 0.0410) expressing puncta in the neuropil of CA3, control group $n = 5$ and dsTeTxLC infected
1048 group $n = 7$. Asterisks in bars indicate statistically significant differences from the control group
1049 after the Student's t-test; $P \leq 0.05$ (*). Abbreviations: vGLUT1: the vesicular glutamate transporter
1050 1 and PSD95: the postsynaptic density 95. **(c)** rAAV-assisted precise targeting of DG and CA3
1051 with tdTOM and EGFP in mouse entorhino-hippocampal slice cultures, respectively, Scale bar =
1052 100 μm . **(d)** Timeline of repetitive confocal imaging. **(e)** Baseline imaging of DG mossy fiber
1053 boutons in the CA3 region of interest (ROI) 1 and 2 (from C) from day 0 (0d) to day 9 (9d) and
1054 Dox-induced dsTeTxLC for 6 days (starting after the imaging at day 3 until day 9) is shown ($n =$

1055 5; 125 mossy fiber boutons total; in one experiment 2 out of 25 boutons were lost after Dox-
1056 induced dsTeTxLC). Scale bars = 50 μm .

